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INTERCOMMUNICATIONS OF THE ART OF POLAND AND AZERBAIJAN

Abstract. Cultural and commercial-economic communications of two countries go away with their roots in the XV century when from Azerbaijan to Poland were brought carpets, silk and cotton. Intercommunications in the sphere of literature and art reach the flourishing in the XIX century. In this time the whole row of literary monuments of Azerbaijan are translated into Polish language and on the contrary. On the boundary of the XIX-XX centuries in Baku there were working magnificent plead of Polish architects – Ioisef Goslavsky, Kazimir Scurevich, Iosif Ploshko, Yevgeniy Skibinsky the works of which decorate the historical centre of the city. The most active in the second half of the XX century were intercommunications in the sphere of fine and folk art. There are also considered examples of two-sided collaboration in the sphere of music, theatre and cinema.

Key words: intercommunications of art, cultural workers, tours, exhibitions, festivals.

Introduction. Cultural interrelations of Azerbaijan and Poland have at least the history of state, diplomatic mutual relations. It is well known that the ruler of Azerbaijan Uzun Hasan in the XV century had close relations with the king of Poland Yagello. In this period there were active trade-economic relations between two countries. Carpets, silk, cotton was brought to Poland from Azerbaijan. In the XVI-XVII centuries Poland at the same time with Germany and England became

one of the biggest consumers and customers of Azerbaijan carpets. In all there were discovered 400 carpets in Poland which were produced in weaving workshops of Sefevi Azerbaijan. State emblems of Poland were often depicted in these carpets. These carpets were known in Europe as “polish” ones.

The interpretation of the main material. In the XIX century cultural relations between Azerbaijan and Poland reached their peak. But the activization of cultural interrelations was connected with dramatic historical events. After the defeat of polish secret organizations in the 1820-s and national-liberation uprising in 1830-1831 many Poles were deported to the Caucasus including Azerbaijan. For these people the life in the Caucasus became their fate. “Here Polish exiles Alexandre (Oles) Khodzko-Boreyko, Yuzef Kovalevsky, Vladislav Strshelnitsky got acquainted with Azerbaijan enlighteners Mirza Jafar Topchubashov, Abbas Gulu agha Bakykhanov” [1]. Oles Khodzko translated Azerbaijan heroic epos “Koroghlu” in the middle of the XIX century and published it in English and French. In 1827 Azerbaijan scientist-orientalist professor of Peterbourg University Mirza Jafar Topchubashov translated into Persian “The Crimean sonnets” of the great Polish poet Adam Mitskevich who he got acquainted with three years ago in Peterbourg. At the same time “A.Bakykhanov and Ismail bay Gutgashenly were in Poland. There Bakykhanov wrote a cycle of poetic works and the treatise “Əsrarül-mələkut” which explains Copernick’s teaching. I.Gutgashenli’s story “Rashid bay and Saadat khanym” which considered to be the first specimen of Azerbaijan prose was firstly published in 1835 in Warsaw” [2].

Hijran Aliyeva in her article “Traces of famous Poles in Azerbaijan” gives a surprizing example of Polish-Azerbaijan literary interrelations. She writes that Azerbaijan is associated with october revolution of 1917, oil-fields and multiculturalism for many Poles. She supposes that it is connected with “events happened in 1917 and 1920 in the capital of Azerbaijan Baku which were presented in Stefan Zheromski’s story “Early spring” (1924) considered by many specialists to be one of the best masterpieces of Polish literature of inter-war period” [6]. However H.Aliyeva goes on, not any admirer of this author knows that Zheromsky himself had never been to Baku, he depicted these events basing on narrations of his girl-friends who returned from Azerbaijan to Poland after october revolution.

Modern state of literary interrelations between Poland and Azerbaijan makes all of us happy. In 2007 there was published the collected stories of 19 Azerbaijan writers including Magsud Ibrahimbayov, Anar, Elchin, Chingiz Abdullayev and others named “Red limousine”. In its turn in 2009 “Antology of modern Polish prose” with tales and stories of famous Polish writers Stanislav Lem, Yezhi Pilkh, Yatsek Dukay and others was published in Azerbaijan. The publishing house “Adam Marshalek” prepared for publishing the novel of the famous Azerbaijan writer and scientist-philologist, Nobel nominee for 2012 Kamal Abdulla [1].

The history of Polish-Azerbaijan interrelations in the sphere of music begins with the name of the great Azerbaijan composer Uzeyir Hajybayli. As it is known the first night of his musical comedy “Arshin mal alan” took place in Baku in 1918. Henceforth “Arshin mal alan” was translated into more than 75 languages and performed in 187 theatres of 76 countries. But this musical comedy was much more performed in Poland. It was staged in 17 towns of Poland about 1500 times!

The famous Polish playwright S.Povolotski remembers: “... I heard for the first time the aria of Asker performed by magnificent singer Rashid Beybutov. Then I saw the film where Rashid Beybutov had played the main role. I was shaken by this film and fell in love with it. Later our favourite singer came to Poland on tour. I heard once more the aria of Asker performed by him in Polish which he sang in each concert. After the next concert I approached Rashid Beybutov and shared my wish to translate “Arshin mal alan” into Polish with him. The singer approved my proposal...” [7].

Having got such a creative urge musical interrelations have been developing in the course of the whole XX century. At the beginning of the XX century one of outstanding Azerbaijan art workers khanende Jabbar Garyaghdyoglu created a trio together with the tarist G.Pirimov and kemancha player S.Ohanezashvili. Their performances in 1906-1912 were recorded in Warsaw on the invitation of joint-stock companies “Gramophone”, “Sport-record” and “Extraphone”. After the 2-nd World War in 1949 a talented pianist Bella Davidovich, a native of Azerbaijan gained a brilliant victory in the fourth International competition of pianists named after Chopin in Warsaw sharing the first prize with Galina Cherni-Stefanskaya and starting with her concert career.

In the opinion of the musicologist professor Zemfira Safarova, mass interest in Polish classic music was aroused by our outstanding

composer Gara Garayev. He took part in the festival “Polish spring” and returning from Poland began actively propagandizing the music of Polish composers Frederich Chopin, Witold Lyontoslavski, Karol Shimanovski, Kshishtof Penderetski and others. In its turn performances of modern Azerbaijan musicians rased great interest in Poland. The first step towards popularity and success for the outstanding singer and composer Muslim Magomayev was his victory in the IX International festival in the town of Sopot in 1969. Later Muslim Magomayev was awarded honorary medal “For services before polish culture”. In 1989 for the first time on Polish radio there were sounded chamber symphony, Country suite and the 6th symphony of the famous Azerbaijan composer Akshin Alizade. “The newspaper “Tribuna opolska” placing the review under the title ‘Azerbaijan music in broadcasts of Polish radio’ noted that A.Alizade’s creation combined traditions of folk music with modern musical palette” [4, p. 89].

Let’s return back for a century. At the turn of the XIX-XX cc. there worked a splendid pleiad [p l a i d] of Polish architects in Baku – Jozef Goslavski, Kazimierz Scorewicz, Jozef Ploszko, Eugeniusz Skibinski. Magnificent buildings which decorate historical centre of Azerbaijan capital were built by them. One of J.Goslavski’s masterpieces is the building of executive committee of Baku. These authors bear a direct relation to big town-planning works carried out in the developing industrial city. Thus according to K.Scorewicz’ project in 1903 there was built and equipped Seaside boulevard in Baku. J.Goslawski was even a chief architect of Baku in 1892-1904. About the creation of these talented architects there is thoroughly spoken in the works of the leading specialist in this sphere professor Shamil Fatullayev including his articles published in Polish language in Warsaw journal “Architecture” published in 1967, 1969 and 1975. I think that those present will be interested in these publications.

Creative heritage of outstanding representatives of Polish culture is carefully preserved and restored. One of magnificent works of J.Goslawski was a dwelling house of the prominent oil magnate and massenas of the XIX-XX cc. Hajy Zeynalabdin Taghiyev in the interiors of which the author used with effect the theme of flaming architecture of Magrib. At present here is placed the National museum of history of Azerbaijan. The facade and interiors of the building were restored three years ago. Design of ceilings and floors of inimitable beauty were re-created. Facades of

historically valuable dwelling houses in 28th May prospect the author of which was the architect J.Ploszko.

In the second half of the XX century Poland also accepted Azerbaijan architects. In 1972 the architect N.Mammadbayli as a member of delegation of the Architects' Union took part in the International meeting of representatives of the East European countries on the theme "New industry – new towns". Our colleague, now unfortunately late professor of Azerbaijan Architecture and Construction University Turan Muradkhanova has got her professional education in Warsaw.

Unlike the architecture, the cinematography is the youngest kind of art. Azerbaijan audience and authors of this report always followed the creation of Polish cinema-men: producers Andjey Vayda and Kshishtof Zanussi, actors Daniel Olbrykhski, Boguslaw Zinda, Barbara Brylska and others. Bilateral collaboration in the sphere of cinema art began in the 1960-s. The delegation of Polish cinematographers headed by deputy minister of culture of Poland Tadeush Zaorski visited Azerbaijan in 1968. The film crew of the film studio "Azerbaijanfilm" shot a documentary film in Poland that year and took part in the V International festival of short film in Krakow. Such works of Azerbaijan authors as "Once there lived", "The queen of lakes", "Shaki palace", "Zeynab Khanlarova", "The hero of taiga" and "It happened in Sandy island" were demonstrated here. Next year during the days of Azerbaijan culture in Poland in the House of soviet culture there was opened the film festival of feature and documentary films produced by the studio "Azerbaijanfilm". In all 10 Azerbaijan films were shown in the House of culture including films about Azerbaijan mugams "Tasnif" and "Shur". Nowadays the participation at the X Baku International film festival "East-West" of the outstanding producer Kshishtof Zanussi was a great event for all true connoisseurs of Polish cinema. Poland was presented by Andjey Yakimovski's film "Trick" in this festival.

Probably Polish-Azerbaijan interrelations in the sphere of fine and folk art were more active in the second half of the XX century. In 1969 during the Days of Azerbaijan culture in Warsaw there was opened the exhibition of painting and sculpture where 47 works of the famous Azerbaijan artists were presented. In 1968 a group of our artists visited Poland, next year Polish colleagues Travinska, Kaspshitski and Gaydugska returned visit. In 1972 graphic artist P.Urovetski and painter P.Brikalski visited Baku. But one of significant events in the sequence of these bilateral contacts

was a creative trip to Poland of the young and promising well painter Togrul Narimanbayov in 1961. Numerous sketches and graphic lists were demonstrated in Baku in his personal exhibition. Landscapes “Maria church” and “Warsaw” especially differed among these works. In 1974 long since well-known and mature artist T.Narimanbayov came to Warsaw with his personal exhibition of works. But not only he derived inspiration from images of Polish culture in his creation. In 1964 the outstanding Azerbaijan sculptor Tokay Mammadov created the portrait of the great Polish composer Frederick Chopin.

There grows the interest of Azerbaijan audience in Polish fine arts. Polish poster enjoyed popularity among professionals and connoisseurs of art in the 1960-1970-s. In 1983 collective exhibition of 42 Polish sculptors was held with great success in Baku. In 1987 on January in the course of two months there was promoted the exhibition “Folk applied art of Azerbaijan” in Gdansk. “The visitors of the exhibition were especially interested in ancient carpets, everyday wares, coinings. Local press published positive views about the exhibition, TV show was dedicated to Azerbaijan folk art” [4, p. 99]. Shortly after at the VIII International biennale of folklore dolls which was held in 1989 in Krakow Azerbaijan artist Elmira Abbasly was awarded the decoration of “Bronze feather of the peacock” and a special prize of the organizing committee for a doll “Nene” (“Grandmother”). At the same time the works of painters Ismail Mammadov, Sara Namitokova-Manafova and Siruz Mirzazade were exhibited in the town of Zelena Gura.

Polish community always played and continues playing a significant role in the social and cultural life of Azerbaijan. At the same time with cultural workers, the sons of the Polish people added glorious pages to Azerbaijan history in various spheres: in policy and state governing, in industry and military science. The Pole Stanislaw Despot-Zenovich was a mayor of Baku in 1879-1894. That time ten Poles were working at the office of Baku governor [8]. Polish engineers P.Pototski and V.Zglenitski made a great contribution to the development of oil industry of Azerbaijan. Speaking at the official reception of the President of Poland Alexandre Kvasnetski, the President of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev in his speech noted that “Brothers Kuchinski were working in the government of Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, chief of staff of the first National army of the first Azerbaijan democratic republic of 1918 was general Sulkevich” [9].

It should be noted that the Polish community in the course of its history differed with its high level of organization. In 1903 the Poles founded “Roman – Catholic Charitable Society” in Baku. There was opened the library and school there. On the 17th of August, 1909 there was registered the society of “Polish house in Baku” the aim of which was cultural development of Polish population [8]. The successor of these traditions is Polish community “Polonia-Azerbaijan” new which was registered on April 24, 2003.

Conclusion. Tours and exhibitions, creative exchange between cultural workers, interrelations in the sphere of art and literature help two peoples to recognize and understand each other. The activity of art masters and scientists, various public and state organizations, representatives of diaspora of two countries made in estimable contribution to the development of relations between Azerbaijan and Poland, turned the centuries – old friendship of our peoples into the reality.

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POLŞA VƏ AZƏRBAYCAN İNCƏSƏNƏTİNİN QARŞILIQLI ƏLAQƏLƏRİ

İki ölkənin mədəni və ticarət-iqtisadi əlaqələri öz kökləri ilə XV əsrə gedib çıxır: o dövrdə Azərbaycandan Polşaya xalçalar, ipək və pambıq gətirirdilər. Ədəbiyyat və incəsənət sahəsində qarşılıqlı əlaqələr XIX yuzillikdə çiçəklənmə dövrünü yaşayır. Bu zaman bir sıra Azərbaycan ədəbi abidələri Polşa dilinə tərcümə olunur və əksinə. XIX-XX əsrlərin kəşiməsində Bakıda bir sıra istedadlı Polşa memarları fəaliyyət göstərir. Yozef Qoslavskiy, Kazimir Skureviç, Yosif Ploşko, Yevgeniy Skibinskiy tərəfindən yaradılmış memarlıq əsərləri şəhərin tarixi mərkəzini bəzəmişlər. XX əsrin ikinci yarısında təsviri və xalq sənətində olan qarşılıqlı əlaqələr olduqca fəal olmuşlar. Məqalədə həmçinin musiqi, teatr və kino sahəsində ikitərəfli əlaqələr nəzərdən keçirilir.

Açar sözlər: incəsənətin qarşılıqlı əlaqələri, mədəniyyət xadimləri, qastrollar, sərgilər, festivallar.

Эртегин Саламзаде, Рена Абдуллаева (Азербайджан)

ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ИСКУССТВА ПОЛЬШИ И АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА

Культурные и торгово-экономические связи двух стран уходят своими корнями в XV век, когда из Азербайджана в Польшу привозили ковры, шелк и хлопок. Взаимосвязи в области литературы и искусства достигают расцвета в XIX столетии. В это время целый ряд литературных памятников Азербайджана переводится на польский язык и наоборот. На рубеже XIX-XX веков в Баку работала блестящая плеяда польских архитекторов – Йозеф Гославский, Казимир Скуревич, Иосиф Плошко, Евгений Скибинский, произведения которых украшают исторический центр города. Наиболее активными во второй половине XX века были взаимосвязи в области изобразительного и народного искусства. В статье рассматриваются также примеры двухстороннего сотрудничества в сфере музыки, театра и кино.

Ключевые слова: взаимосвязи искусства, деятели культуры, гастроли, выставки, фестивали.